

ISic3490

I.Sicily inscription 3490

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---]HENT[---]

2. [---]HYTA[---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645111

EDR 140747

EDCS 41300109

PHI 175751

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.

Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 146

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